

**Manuel Alejandro
De Oliveira Da Costa**

**Abordagens computacionais para o estudo da fala na
comunicação em grupos.**

**Computational approaches to study speech
communication in groups**

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Dissertação apresentada à Universidade de Aveiro para cumprimento dos requisitos necessários à obtenção do grau de Mestre em Engenharia de Computadores e Telemática, realizada sob a orientação científica do Doutor Samuel de Sousa Silva, Investigador no Instituto de Engenharia Electrónica e Informática de Aveiro (IEETA) da Universidade de Aveiro, e da Doutora Susana Manuela Martinho dos Santos Baía Brás, Investigadora no Instituto de Engenharia Electrónica e Informática de Aveiro (IEETA) da Universidade de Aveiro.

Dedico este trabalho aos meus sobrinhos Diego e Enzo.

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Palavras Chave

Áudio, Processamento de fala, Comunicação, Voz, Dinâmicas de Grupo, Processamento de Sinal, Aprendizagem Não-Supervisionada

Resumo

Grupos são entidades importantes na nossa vida quotidiana, seja em contextos sociais, como em família, ou profissionais, como no trabalho. A nossa identidade é moldada pelos diversos grupos aos quais pertencemos, do mesmo modo que a identidade destes é caracterizada pelos seus membros.

As interações entre os elementos de um grupo criam um conjunto de dinâmicas inter-pessoais que têm um impacto direto no desempenho das tarefas realizadas pelos mesmos. A produtividade dos grupos correlaciona-se com as dinâmicas existentes, onde a comunicação tem um papel central.

O desenvolver da comunicação no grupo evidencia as suas dinâmicas existentes e a maneira como as mesmas evoluem ao longo do tempo. Estudando estas dinâmicas é possível compreender melhor as mecânicas de funcionamento do grupo que, por sua vez, podem explicar alguns fenómenos, como a qualidade do trabalho desenvolvido em equipa.

A comunicação permite aos elementos do grupo expressar as suas ideias, crenças e sentimentos, possibilitando a articulação do trabalho desenvolvido pelo grupo. A fala, sendo a nossa forma mais natural de comunicação, viabiliza estas interações tendo assim um papel predominante nestes contextos.

Neste trabalho realiza-se um estudo objetivo e sistemático às características descritoras da voz que permitem representar a comunicação baseada na fala em grupos. Mais ainda, são estudadas mecânicas de interação inter-pessoais, em circunstâncias de pequenos grupos, e as dinâmicas sociais por si evidenciadas. Neste contexto, pretende-se contribuir com uma abordagem computacional que permita analisar, de uma maneira robusta, a comunicação baseada na fala em grupos.

Para isto, é efetuada uma revisão literária sobre os conceitos teóricos da comunicação baseada na fala, da voz e de dinâmicas de grupos. Com base nestes estudos, foi proposta uma ferramenta prova de conceito que articula as diferentes etapas do processamento de fala que viabilizam o estudo das interações inter-pessoais e das dinâmicas de grupo.

Para demonstrar a aplicabilidade dos métodos propostos é efetuado um estudo exploratório sobre uma base de dados de fala relativos a grupos em situações de conflito em tarefas colaborativas. Os resultados obtidos mostram sinais promissores, permitindo evidenciar e distinguir automaticamente diferentes tipos de conflito com base em características descritoras da fala previamente estudadas.

Keywords

Audio, Speech Processing, Communication, Voice, Group Dynamics, Signal Processing, Unsupervised Learning

Abstract

Groups are important entities in our daily life, whether in social contexts, such as family, or professional, as at work. Our identity is shaped by the various groups to which we belong, in the same way that their identity is characterized by their members.

The interactions between the members of a group create a set of inter-personal dynamics that have a direct impact on the performance of the tasks performed by them. The productivity of the groups correlates with the existing dynamics, where communication plays a central role.

The development of communication in the group highlights its existing dynamics and the way they evolve over time. By studying these dynamics it is possible to better understand the mechanics of the group's functioning which, in turn, may explain some phenomena such as the quality of teamwork.

Communication allows the members of the group to express their ideas, beliefs and feelings that allow to articulate the work done by the group. Speech, being our most natural form of communication, makes these interactions possible and thus plays a predominant role in these contexts.

In this work an objective and systematic study is made of the descriptive characteristics of the voice that allow the representation of communication based on speech in groups. Furthermore, interpersonal interaction mechanics are also studied, in the circumstances of small groups, and the social dynamics evidenced by them. In this context, it is intended to contribute with a computational approach that allows to analyze, in a robust way, the communication based on speech in groups. To this end, a review on literature is carried out on the theoretical concepts of speech-based communication, voice and group dynamics. Based on these studies, a proof-of-concept tool was proposed that articulates the different stages of speech processing that make the study of interpersonal interactions and group dynamics possible.

To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed methods, an exploratory study is carried out on a database containing speech relating to groups in conflict situations during collaborative tasks. The results obtained show promising findings, allowing different types of conflict to be automatically identified and distinguished based on the descriptive characteristics of speech previously studied.

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Glossary

VAD	Voice Activation Detection	SDS	Spoken Dialog System
FCR	Floor Control Ratio	FPR	False Positive Rate
ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition	TPR	True Positive Rate
SNR	Speech-to-noise Ratio	MFCC	Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficient
GMM	Gussian Mixture Model	ZCR	Zero Cross Rating
HMM	Hidden Markov Model	CCR	Relational Conflict Condition
EOU	End of Utterance	CCT	Task Conflict Condition
IVR	Interactive Voice Response	CC	Control Condition
VPA	Virtual Personal Assistant		

Introduction

In this chapter an introduction is made to the subject of this thesis. To this end, a contextualization of the topic is provided. Then, the motivations that led to the realization of this work are presented followed by a description of several challenges associated with it. Deriving from the identified challenges, a set of objectives is defined that guide the study to be carried out. Lastly, a brief description of the document's organization is presented.

1.1 VERBAL COMMUNICATION AND GROUPS

Verbal communication has a central role in our lives [1]. The ability to express ourselves about virtually anything has a pivotal role on how we live in society. Through it, we are able to express our ideas and needs, and coordinate actions to fulfill goals [2] both in our personal and professional lives. We are constantly communicating with others and we do it in a very natural way.

It is as crucial to our lives as it is complex to study and understand, especially in groups where there are several participants engaged in conversation. Such scenarios have become increasingly common and relevant in the current society, making the study of verbal communication in groups an even more relevant thematic.

1.2 MOTIVATION

Groups are preponderant entities in our daily life. We often organize ourselves into groups in order to create joint efforts to solve the most diverse challenges that arise in our personal and professional lives. Groups are composed by people that sustain social interactions among themselves, creating dynamics that are strongly related to the well-being of its members and, consequently, to the group's harmony and productivity.

Within the groups, communication assumes a fundamental role by enabling the messages of the members to be conveyed, either to express their ideas and feelings or to carry out actions such as instructing other members. The coordination of the group, such as the division

of tasks, is usually discussed and agreed among the team members in order to optimize the group's organization to accomplish tasks more efficiently and with better outcomes. In general, it is possible to infer how a team works together or how it is organised by analysing the group's communication patterns. Since communication has such a central role in supporting the group's performance, failures in communication, such as the monopoly of communication by a single member, can disrupt the group's activities and, in turn, aspects such as conflict among group members, or even tiredness, might reflect on the communication. Therefore, an understanding of how the group communication is unveiling might shed some light on how the work might be progressing and provide some insights on the group's performance and context, along with the status of each member, which can guide, e.g., the team manager on balancing and coordinating the team's efforts.

Even though we are able to intuitively assess conversations, detect patterns and categorize its actors, we want to understand what is behind our natural capacity of doing it. If we are able to understand this, we can transpose this knowledge to computational systems and perform semi and fully automatic speech analysis.

In this context, the study of group communication using computational resources can also become an important resource in several scenarios that can automatically exploit information on social dynamics to their benefit, such as automatic dialogue analysis systems that might generate reports on team communication. These systems could be used by the teams in order to optimize their communication processes and, consequently, the teams' productivity. Additionally, intelligent systems such as meeting mediators that might detect latent conflict or unbalanced communication among team members could also be an important resource in organizations.

1.3 CHALLENGES

The study of verbal communication is a multi-disciplinary and complex task that raises many challenges during its analysis. The theoretical studies and formulations on diverse aspects of communication raise a number of challenges inherent to the abstract nature of the concept of communication itself. On the other hand, the computational analysis of dialogue requires a careful approach both in the choice of speech processing techniques and in the computational definition of the relevant communication's descriptive characteristics.

- **Speech communication is a complex phenomenon.** Human dialogue is a continuous, ongoing process [1] that is highly spontaneous and interactive. During a conversation we are constantly analysing diverse aspects that surround us that make us react and adapt. Moreover, a conversation is composed of several people who have distinct ideas, characteristic behaviors and different perceptions which motivate unique and complex interactions. Verbal communication is also influenced by factors of a non-verbal nature that have an impact on the outcome of the conversation and its members [3][4]. In example, our stance in a dialogue is influenced by elements that may not be related with the verbal communication that is taking place.

- **Speech communication analysis needs to be supported on objective descriptors.** Although we have a natural relationship with communication, it is a great challenge to understand what our interpretation is based on and, therefore, defining these characteristics is not a trivial task. There are some studies to guide us but there is no global definition of **what** is, or not, a good descriptor to expose communication patterns. Moreover, when working with computational approaches, there is the increased difficulty that these characteristics must be transferred to computational systems that depend on precise measurements of data to be able to operate. This entails moving from a subjective appreciation of the communication, as we do it, in our daily lives, into meaningful objective measures of the phenomenon.
- **Communication within groups is complicated.** The communication process is a complicated phenomenon that depends on many factors [1], which makes social interactions to be messy. In groups, this gains even more notorious dimensions given the individuals actions and interactions, and the effects that they have on other members since the individuals behaviors are also influenced by the group as a whole [5]. There is an inter-dependability between individuals and the group that creates heterogeneous behaviors that are more difficult to address.
- **Real life audio recordings are noisy.** The ability to perform automated analyses on speech relies on many components that require state of the art techniques to retrieve data from speech signals. There are several sources that can introduce errors in the analysis at various stages of the process and, therefore, it is necessary to ensure that these errors are expected, measured and controlled to guarantee a cleaner and more robust final analysis.

As today, dealing with unexpected noise in speech signals is still an issue that varies from study to study. Some techniques to deal with it are more adequate in certain scenarios than others and, consequently, it is vital to understand which are suitable for this study and which are not. In group meetings there are limitless possibilities of unexpected scenarios that might interfere with the speech signals, ranging from improper microphone usage to unexpected technical issues with hardware or unforeseen events within the meeting itself.

- **Modelling conversations computationally is error-prone.** In order to model interactions during dialogue it is necessary to define a set of behaviors for each individual that can potentially contain information about the flow of the conversation. For example, a person that constantly interrupts others might be associated with a dominant profile which in turn is a behaviour that may highlight the existence of conflicts within the group. These behaviours are approximated by characteristics that are measured through the participants' speech and, for this, a speech's signal must be transformed into a logical framework that we can extract these conversational features, such as how often a person interrupts another. This process alone has a wide variety of issues that require special attention and study to guarantee reliable approximations of the communicative process.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this dissertation is the conceptual design and development of a computational tool to support the study of social dynamics in group settings. The following objectives are then defined in order to achieve this:

- Perform a literature research to select the most relevant aspects of communication for the study of social dynamics in dialogue.
- Propose computational methods, based on the researched literature, to quantify the relevant speech features for the study of communication.
- Develop a proof-of-concept tool, based on the proposed methods, to support the study of social dynamics in groups based on speech.
- Validate the relevance of the proposed methods and test their applicability as tools to analyse and foster an insight over dialogue analyses.

It is also one of the objectives of this work to be able to add some knowledge to the research effort already carried out in this area by scholars from the Universidade de Aveiro. These works also analyse the attitude of individuals during meetings in order to highlight the social strategies employed by them.

1.5 THESIS STRUCTURE

This document is structured in five chapters. In chapter 2 a summary is provided of related work in the area of speech processing and communication dynamics deemed relevant to this thesis. Furthermore, a review is made of works in the area of Psychology which exploit social dynamics in communication, and whose contribution to the knowledge of this field is invaluable in the context of recent approaches to this topic, such as the one proposed here. In chapter 3, it is detailed all the work done regarding the design and implementation of the proposed computational methods to process and analyse speech communication dynamics. In chapter 4, the study case chosen for this work is mentioned. It also contains the details about the results of the communicative patterns analysis performed on the selected database. Lastly, in chapter 5, the performed work is discussed as well as topics for future works that may evolve or profit from this one.

Background and Related Work

In this chapter, an overview is made of the literature on communication deemed relevant to this dissertation. A set of studies is explored related to the theoretical formulations on speech and group dynamics that are the foundations for the computational approach of this work. Afterwards, the computational aspects of speech processing are mentioned. Firstly, the voice is analysed, in terms of its physical properties, and how it can be detected automatically. Following this, some works are analyzed that focus on the study of speech in dialogue and the interaction dynamics between the intervenients. Finally, a set of representative toolkits for speech processing is mentioned and audio databases that are commonly used in related works are also presented.

2.1 SPEECH COMMUNICATION

A possible definition of human communication is that it is the process of intentionally exchanging **information** between **peers** [6]. It is a rather complex and abstract process and its study is influenced by many factors. The perception of communication varies by **context**: how many persons are involved, who are the participants, how the information is exchanged, among others. Our approach to a conversation within family members is not the same as with work colleagues or friends. The same rationale applies to varying group sizes, the subject of the conversation and whether we are communicating face-to-face or through the internet.

The exchange of information between peers is carried out through messages transmitted in certain channels such as writing or speech. The choice of the communication channel has a considerable impact not only on the dynamics of the communication but also on the effect of the message that is transmitted [1]. For example, the act of face-to-face negotiation encompasses a set of behaviors, such as brevity, which have a significant impact on the outcome of the negotiation. These behaviors might not be represented in other channels such as e-mails, where peers have a larger time window to process information and to formulate an answer. The characteristics of the actor's voice transmit sensations that influence the course of the communication process and its actors, which are not found in other channels.

Another aspect to consider in the study of communication is the number of participants involved. Depending on the number of speakers, there are different aspects of communication that stand out. In a dialogue between two people, a dyad, it is possible to capture individual indicators that help to describe the conversation and its outcome. These same indicators may be irrelevant in characterising another context, such as a public discourse. In the case of a small group, where all its members participate actively in the discussion [1], the number of participants is reduced and the interactions maintained between them create specific group dynamics. Therefore, it is relevant to consider the quality of the communication and how it unveils when studying small groups in order to understand its dynamics.

2.2 SPEECH CHARACTERISTICS AND GROUP DYNAMICS

Speech as our main form of communication is a very familiar aspect in everyday life and is an obvious choice for many people [1]. The voice contains physical properties that add value to the message that is transmitted and provides information that is not included in the message content. Prosody properties such as intonation and intensity play an important part in speech [7] and can be used to highlight the message or to convey feelings. In extreme cases it is the use of these characteristics that allows to decode the message and its meaning.

The characteristics of speech support the study of the context of communication, as well as the behaviors associated with interpersonal interactions during the dialogue. In the study conducted by De Pasquale, Cullen, and Vaughan [8] the authors explore speech and its prosodic characteristics to highlight events that indicate synchronism between participants in psychotherapeutic interventions. In particular, they investigate coordinating behaviors in speech, like prosodic accommodation, as indicators of feelings such as empathy which, in turn, are correlated with the success of patient-therapist relationships. The authors also explore some relationships, such as the rapport, which can be evidenced through the study of speech.

In terms of speech production, speakers may adapt their speech to emphasize parts of the message that is transmitted or even to aggregate more information such as sentiments. For example, pause times between sentences support the speaker's attitude in the dialogue, outlining a certain stance to others regarding the conversation's topic. In the work developed by Hung and Gatica-Perez [9], the authors study group cohesion in working teams. For this, they use as hypothesis a set of characteristics of speech and its production, such as the pause times between sentences, in order to infer a team's cohesion levels. Moreover, studies conducted to the speech rate, i.e. how fast or slow people talk, correlate it with the expression of sentiments, such as anger [10], and feelings synchronization between speakers [9].

In organizations and groups, communication plays a predominant role [2]. It supports the coordination of actions involving multiple parties that need to cooperate in order to achieve common objectives. In the work developed by Rysman and Weissenberg [2], the authors study the behavior of people in the context of organizations. Organizations are entities composed of complex networks of people in which each one has a role to perform. The authors emphasize the importance of communication in the performance of some roles which directly affects

the productivity of the work groups. Ultimately, the groups dynamics are related to the productivity of the organizations.

These conclusions are also corroborated by the work carried out by Hassall [11], in which the authors explore the relationship of communication and teams. They argue that groups can be characterized by their communicative profiles which, in turn, have a direct impact on their performance. The relationship between communication and working groups is explored in the literature in other works where the purpose is to study group dynamics, such as cohesion [9] and team performance [3]. Authors argue that these social dynamics can be analysed by the interactions sustained between teams, which in turn are characterized by speech indicators, such as the groups speech and overlap time.

2.3 COMPUTATIONAL METHODS FOR SPEECH CHARACTERIZATION

The computational analysis of speech is divided into two major approaches. On the one hand, it is possible to use the transcription of speech in order to study the content of the message. This approach requires the use of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) methods which transcribe everything that is spoken into text. This technique allows capturing information regarding the topic of the conversation, the type of vocabulary used by each participant, among others. For example, in the study developed by Rienks, Zhang, Gatica-Perez, *et al.* [12], the authors explore the transcriptions to support the study of the influence of each member in small groups.

On the other hand, speech communication can be analysed without using transcripts of what is being said. That is, verbal communication is studied in terms of **how** people speak and how their voice sounds. This concept is intuitive to humans since we have the natural capability to, for example, differentiate statements and questions just by the intonation of the end of the sentence or understanding whether a certain word has a certain connotation. Many studies suggest that we are able to understand different aspects of human-to-human communication, such as rapport, mimicry and adaptability [8] [13], by computationally analysing acoustic and prosodic features of the audio signals without the need to understand what is being said.

Finally, audio signals can provide more information than what is extracted from their physical properties. Starting from a speech signal it is possible to build a framework that conceptualizes and explores dialogue between participants which, in a final stage, allow us to better understand the communicative process. This process can be modelled in terms of turn taking behavior, overlaps or interruptions, among others, that contain information not only on the social dynamics and interactions between people [14] [15] but also on people themselves [16].

2.3.1 Voice analysis for studying speech

Human speech is produced through vocal sounds generated by a source, in this case the speaker. It is a mechanical process that encompasses a set of parts of the human vocal tract which, in a final stage, produces sounds in the form of sound waves. These waves can be captured through the use of specialized electronic equipment that allows their modelling and

analysis. As a result, a digital signal is produced that can be studied using signal theory methods. This whole process allows the computational modeling of voice and, consequently, speech.

Voice features

The signal produced by the voice is a wave which contains a set of physical properties that characterize it. There are two types of speech characteristics that are addressed in this revision given their preponderance in computational speech analysis: acoustic and prosodic features. On the one hand, the signal contains a set of acoustic characteristics related to physical properties of the voice such as energy and pitch. On the other hand, the prosodic characteristics are related to the production of speech such as intonation and rhythm.

The energy present in the signal is a property that is often used for speech analysis in the recent literature. It is used by methods of voice activity detection, which will be mentioned later in this work, and in speech studies. For example, in the work done by Hung and Gatica-Perez [9], the authors use acoustic properties of the voice, such as the energy, in the study of speech to model behaviors that may indicate intra-group cohesion.

Energy can be computed using different methods that exist in the signal theory literature and each one is more suitable for different cases of application. For example, the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) are a set of characteristics that represent the energy existing in lower frequencies of the signal. A particularity of these characteristics is that they are based on the calculation of energy on the Mel frequency scale, which in turn is suitable for the analysis of speech signals. This scale allows the extraction of energy to be focused on frequencies suitable for human speech, approximating the human auditory system.

These characteristics are often used in literature for speech analysis in various contexts [5], [17], [18]. The work developed by Lian, Tao, Liu, *et al.* [5] studies the emotional states of speakers during conversations using deep learning methods that use acoustic properties of the signal, such as the MFCCs, as input for the neural networks classifiers.

Another major feature that is often used in speech analysis is pitch. The pitch is characterized as the fundamental frequency of the signal, F_0 , and its use is also frequent in the literature. It is calculated in the frequency domain and, like energy, there are several methods for pitch extraction. In the work done by Jouviet and Laprie [19] a meta analysis is made of the different pitch extraction techniques. The authors explore various algorithms and compare their performances under different noise conditions in order to understand the algorithms suitability for different scenarios. Findings show that noise has a very relevant impact on the performance of the different methods and, therefore, it might be appropriate to use different techniques in different cases.

Pitch is commonly used by Voice Activation Detection (VAD) algorithms [20], where pitch formations represent possible voiced segments. However, this information is not used in isolation and speech detection algorithms usually combine pitch with other signal properties such as the Zero Cross Rating (ZCR). Additionally, pitch also contains information about speech that is used for studies of conversational dynamics, as in the study conducted by

Aldeneh, Jaiswal, Picheny, *et al.* [13]. Authors explore variations in mood episodes of patients with bi-polar disorder and use the variations of pitch to identify the patients mood states.

Prosodic characteristics are related to the production of speech and play an important role in the course of a conversation. They characterize the variation of rhythm and intonation that contain information on syllables [13] and other linguistic aspects. They are commonly used in conversational dynamics studies given that they support the highlighting of words and sentences that evidence contexts, such as feelings [9], that can explain certain social behaviors in inter-personal interactions [13].

Voice Detection

VAD algorithms are a common type of algorithms which are vital to a wide variety of speech systems around the world such as ASR, audio surveillance or speaker identification applications [21]. It performs a specialized analysis on audio signals in order to distinguish voiced segments from background noise [21]. A classic VAD algorithm starts by extracting a set of features, commonly in the frequency domain such as the ZCR, pitch or energy, and uses them as input to discriminatory models that will establish a threshold to separate voiced from unvoiced segments.

It is important that a VAD algorithm is able to perform a robust analysis not only in clean but also in noisy environments [22] since, in real world applications, audio data is more unpredictable and may contain a considerable amount of clattering.

These algorithms have evolved over time given the growing demand for robust audio recognition systems that can operate in real-life scenarios. Traditional VAD algorithms decisions relied on simpler models that defined static thresholds or combined different features [21]. Later, more complex techniques were proposed that adapt their decision threshold dynamically to the acoustic environment by taking into account the background noise, Speech-to-noise Ratio (SNR) of each channel, among others [22].

With the growing interest in speech processing, new features and techniques have gained preponderance in the speech analysis domain. These developments have been accompanied, and boosted, by the development of other statistical disciplines due to their suitability for speech processing. Studies found that the task of detecting voiced and unvoiced segments can be modelled using likelihood ratio tests, with models such as Gussian Mixture Models (GMMs) and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) being frequently used. More recently, due to the emergence of machine learning and the exponential increase in computational capacity, VAD methods are broadly categorized in supervised and unsupervised methods. Supervised methods rely on labelled data to train classifiers, such as neural networks, that may outperform unsupervised methods if the testing environment's noise conditions are similar to the training [20]. Thus, they may fail to generalize for broader scenarios due to the unpredictability of the noise that is produced in different cases. On the other hand, unsupervised methods try to make decisions independently of the situation on which it is used. They are mainly a continuation of the previous studies that were based on statistical models and, therefore, do not have any dependency on labelled data and do not rely on any assumptions about the

noise conditions. Nonetheless, as previously mentioned, the usage of unsupervised methods should consider the noise conditions of the study that is being performed in order to maximise the algorithm’s performance in terms of voice detection.

In group meetings there is a specific source of noise that interferes heavily with VAD algorithms. Namely, due to the physical proximity between audio sources, the recorded audio for one source can be a mixture of several signals, as shown in Figure 2.1. This is a known phenomenon called cross-talk, or microphone bleeding, that requires special attention. When considering one speaker’s speech, there are two scenarios that should be considered: 1. The recorded audio is a mixture of other participants speech without containing any activity from the considered speaker; 2. The recorded audio is a mixture of other participants speech with the current speaker talking in overlap. Previous studies refer to these scenarios as “cross-talk only” and “cross-talk plus speaker” [18], respectively. Moreover, in speech meetings the dialogue is typically spontaneous frequently resulting in situations where speakers overlap their speech with each other [18], which makes it even more difficult to differentiate between overlap situations and cross-talk.

The choice of the microphone type used in the experiments has a major influence in both cross-talk ratio and how it can be handled. Previous studies show that personal headset configurations reveal better performances in cross-talk detection [23] even compared to lapel microphones, but, nonetheless, microphone bleeding remains a challenge that require further processing to tackle it [18].

Figure 2.1: Example of a cross talk situation. Audio waveform, spectrogram and pitch formations comparison between two participants in the same meeting. The left one is speaking while the other is silent. In the spectrograms, darker segments refer to frames containing considerable amounts of energy in the speech frequency range. Blue outlines drawn on top of the spectrograms indicate pitch formations. Even though only one is speaking, there are pitch formations and detected energy segments in the right participant’s signal.

Cross-talk detection can be considered a type of speaker diarization because, in fact, we are dealing with a signal mixture that contains speech from more than one source and we

are interested in separating them. Nonetheless, in cases where participants wear their own headset, this task can be performed using more alternative techniques than the ones used in classic speaker separation.

Many studies have been conducted about this topic and it has proven to be a tough challenge, especially in real applications [24] [18]. Many studies are based on the research by Wrigley, Brown, Wan, *et al.* [18], who performed an exhaustive study and tested a wide variety of features such as MFCC, pitch, energy, ZCR and short-time signal kurtosis. Their findings show that the best features for cross-talk detection, in their study, were mainly the short-time kurtosis and cross-correlation metrics.

2.3.2 Conversation analysis based on speech

Contemporary literature contains a set of computational studies aimed at dialogue-based communication analysis. To this end, many of these studies begin by characterizing the dialogue from the conceptual point of view. In this way, it is possible to create a computational framework that allows describing interpersonal interactions and represent social dynamics among participants.

Utterances

VAD provides important information about speech that can be further processed to conceptualize communication. One possible approach is to segment the VAD output by grouping contiguous voiced segments into what can be called as **utterances**. Many studies are based on the theoretical formulations by Duncan [25]–[28] and Sacks, Schegloff, and Jefferson [29], who argue that human dialogue is perpetuated following a turn-based interaction. This process can be referred as utterance segmentation, turn segmentation or End of Utterance (EOU) detection. EOU detection is a common processing stage for many ASR systems such as Interactive Voice Response (IVR) [30] and personal assistant [31] systems.

Virtual Personal Assistant (VPA) systems have gained visibility in the last decade and its popularity has increased dramatically in the recent years with the emergence of commercial products, such as Amazon’s AlexaTM ¹, Apple’s SiriTM ² or Google’s AssistantTM ³. Some of these systems are trying to create more realistic agents by allowing the user to communicate using continuous speech instead of command-based interactions. For this, the system must be able to detect the end of a speaker’s turn to process the information given by the speaker.

On the other hand, IVR applications are commonly used as a first stage for handling requests in customer services, in an attempt to reduce the need for human intervention to address common issues that users might have. State of the art IVR systems are developing technologies that allow users to interact using voiced utterances instead of text-based commands.

In an effort to create smoother interactions between users and automatic systems, turn segmentation gained relevance and, consequently, many studies emerged in this area. One

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of the main issues with automatic systems is that user’s EOU detection is not a trivial task, especially when the user’s interactions are not command-based. Continuous speech is more unpredictable [32] and the EOUs are not as easily detected since there is no set of predetermined words, or commands, that the system is expecting to find. This is aggravated by short utterances, or back-channel responses, such as “uh-uh” or “mm-hm” that humans frequently use [30], [33]. If the turn segmentation is not done properly, an automatic system will often interrupt the user [31] creating an unpleasant experience thus deteriorating the quality of the system and its usability. More recently, efforts have been made to apply EOU detection to continuous speech, not only to human-to-machine interactions but also to study human-to-human communication [34] [35].

There are several turn segmentation strategies and the suitability of each one varies across use cases. In this work we are interested in segmenting continuous human-to-human speech and, therefore, some of these studies will be analysed.

One simple definition of an EOU is that a turn ends whenever the speaker stops talking for a certain amount of time. This silence timeout approach was used in conventional Spoken Dialog Systems (SDSs) [33], and the timeout threshold typically ranges from 0.5 to 1 s [36]. This strategy was widely used for many years, but nowadays it is not considered a very robust one [30], [33]. More complex techniques are being studied that approach this problem as a classification task [35] based on extracted features that proved to be strong cues of turn shifts [30]. Authors take into consideration the previous speaker’s utterances to predict its next EOUs, using both locally and globally extracted features for each speaker. Additionally, some studies try to relate the EOU with the physical properties of the speech’s signal such as pitch [33]. The authors explore the possibility of detecting final and non-final pauses based on the acoustic properties of each individual’s speech signal. This has an intuitive interpretation since we, as humans, seem to use these acoustic features in order to predict the other speaker’s EOU. Usually, the intonation of the end of a sentence tends to indicate that the speaker is finishing his turn and, therefore, giving the floor to other speakers. However, if the EOU does not become evident by the intonation we assume that the other speaker is having a non-final pause within his own turn.

Speech features for studying inter-personal interactions in dialogue

With a robust framework that detects each speaker’s start and end of utterances, it is possible to computationally explore human-to-human communication in an effort to understand the interactions between speakers and their social dynamics.

Researchers have gained interest in this field due to the increasing demand on understanding conversational patterns in human-to-human interactions. On the one hand, there is a notable interest in intelligent communicative systems that may use this knowledge to evolve to more realistic agents. On the other hand, understanding communication has a wide variety of uses in organizations, education and health. There are many applications where these insights are vital such as measuring the communication’s impact on meetings outcomes [37]; modelling medical interactions [8]; and providing insights to team leaders in order to improve engineering

design activities [38].

Communication analysis with computational resources can be as complex as desired ranging from understanding simple concepts, such as speaking time, to more complex phenomena such as performing sentiment analysis.

The first studied set of features are based on each participant's speech time. The total speech time of groups is explored by Hung and Gatica-Perez [9] as an indicator for estimating cohesion levels within teams. Authors argue that higher volumes of voiced activity is linked to higher levels of harmony. However, if speakers are constantly speaking at the same time, **overlapping** each other, it may be a manifestation of conflict. Additionally, the speech time can be used as indicator of behaviors such as dominance [39] and leadership. In the work by Jayagopi, Hung, Yeo, *et al.* [40], the authors studied a set of audio-visual cues to assess dominance in group conversations. The authors findings indicate that the amount of speech produced is a strong cue for dominance perception by humans.

The speech time's distribution among participants can also be seen as an indicator of dominance if its distribution is uneven across the dialogue. This feature is referred as Floor Control Ratio (FCR) and defined as the relative amount of speech time for each speaker to the total amount of speech in the conversation [13]. It is explored as a dominance indicator based on the theory that more submissive speakers may end up giving the floor to more dominant speakers [41], even as a way of social accommodation, that is reflected on the unbalanced distribution of speech time.

Based on speaker's turn-taking behavior, many features are explored in the literature to explain a vast array of social phenomena. Studies found that turns of dominant individuals tend to be more extensive and more frequent [42] while the amount of consecutive turns may indicate that individuals are willing to assume leadership roles within the group [13]. Lai and Murray [43] studied methods of predicting group satisfaction in meetings by using conversational features extracted from the turn-taking behaviors of the participants. Their study found that the turn-taking mechanics are strongly correlated with the participant's satisfaction of the meeting.

The act of overlapping is referred to as a situation where two people speak at the same time, disregarding the social rules of turn-taking. It is hypothesized as an indicator of conflict and lack of group cohesion. In the work by Hung and Gatica-Perez [9], authors found that the speaking rate of the participants while in overlap situations is a good indicator for estimating a group's cohesion. Nonetheless, it is also interesting to note that overlapping is not always referred as a negative sign in terms of communication, as studied by Sacks, Schegloff, and Jefferson [29] who found that it is a natural phenomenon that can be associated to a predictive behavior that humans have regarding each others speech, as an effort to sustain smoother conversations with small gaps between speakers turns. It is important to differentiate situations of natural overlap from scenarios where the overlap occurs over extended periods of time, which become an unpleasant experience for the speakers.

Other cues can be derived from the turn-taking dynamics that are relevant to assess conflicts in face-to-face interactions. The interruption mechanics between speakers is theoretically

studied as a possible indicator of an individual’s personalities [44]. This hypothesis is further explored computationally in more recent studies [15], where authors explore the correlation between participant’s personality traits and overlapping and interrupting dynamics. These traits refer to the Big-5 personality traits [45], which can be associated with conflicts in terms of group’s performances [3]. On the other hand, Robinson and Reis [46] explores the effects of interruptions on interpersonal perceptions. The results obtained by the authors suggest that interruptions are linked to more negative personality assignments and that interruptors are seen as less sociable and more assertive than interruptees. There are also very interesting studies associating the mechanics of interruption with the people’s gender and the way that people of different genders interact with each other [46], [47].

2.4 AUDIO PROCESSING TOOLS

The computational exploration of speech is made through the use of tools specialized in signal analysis and mathematical computation. There are also tools that focus only in speech processing, which already include a set of libraries that provide the necessary operations for speech analysis.

The library SciPy [48] provides robust tools for signal processing and also for scientific computations [49], such as statistical and linear algebraic libraries. It is a core library for the development of applications in Python [50] that require mathematical calculations, as in scientific research.

Praat [51] is a software specialized in audio analysis and manipulation, more specifically speech. This software provides visualization tools that are used in literature for speech inspection. It also contains methods for computing audio signal’s characteristics that can be extracted and used in various programmatic environments.

Praat has a Python interface called Parselmouth [52], which provides the programmer with a set of Praat software features, such as pitch extraction, without leaving the Python’s environment.

It is worth to mention that the library OpenSMILE [53] is a widely used tool for speech processing in state-of-the-art works, as in [5]. It provides tools to extract features from speech signals that can be used by other tools.

2.5 PUBLICLY AVAILABLE SPEECH DATASETS FOR STUDYING SOCIAL DYNAMICS

There have been many studies that perform social dynamics analysis based on speech. Some studies differ in the databases that they use, to fit their needs for their particular studies. These databases might contain audio data recorded in “controlled” environments where speakers act as “voice actors”, this is, they are not recorded in a real-life scenario and, therefore, the post-processing techniques required are not the same as in real-world cases. On the other hand, some databases contain recorded data from real-life interactions such as clinical interviews [8] [13]. Some notable examples of these databases are presented below.

The PRIORI - Predicting Individual Outcomes for Rapid Intervention [54] - data set contains cellphone recordings of individuals diagnosed with Bi-Polar disorder. The participants are recorded for as long as 13 months in interactions maintained with a clinician on a weekly base. On top of it, they are also recorded in personal calls. The annotated data for this database comes in two forms: i) from the clinicians weekly assessment and ii) from manual annotation about the emotional expressions from the patients. The data set provides over 380 hours of speech.

The MELD - Multi Modal Emotionlines Dataset [55] - database comprises more than 1400 dialogues and 13000 utterances from the worldwide famous TV show Friends™. It contains audio, text and video data for all the conversations. The dialogues are replicated by speakers and they are annotated in terms of emotions and sentiments. Each utterance is labeled as Anger, Disgust, Sadness, Joy, Neutral, Surprise or Fear in terms of emotions and as positive, negative or neutral in terms of sentiments [55]. MELD has more than 1400 dialogues and 13000 utterances from Friends TV series.

Many other studies work with specific databases suited for their needs. In example, Ludusan and Wagner [56] perform laughter dynamics analysis to assess social aspects such as convergence, synchronism and agreement between participants from different socio-cultural contexts (German, French and Chinese). They make use of the DUEL [57] database which contains around 24 hours of spontaneous conversations in French, German and Mandarin Chinese.

Sudhakar and Anil [58] perform a review study and mentions databases such as DES (The Danish Emotional Speech Database) and BES (The Berlin Emotional Speech Database) as ones of the most famous databases for emotion detection. Both contain annotated data in terms of emotions for “voice actors” reading texts, in a similar way to what is done by Livingstone and Russo [59] in the widely famous RAVDESS (The Ryerson Audio-Visual Database of Emotional Speech and Song).

Recently, an effort has been made at the Universidade de Aveiro to build a novel data set for studying speech communication in groups, more specifically to study the emergence of conflicts within teams, which serves as grounds for the work presented in this dissertation.

Computational methods for speech communication analysis in groups

This chapter addresses the computational methods to study speech in groups proposed in this dissertation, and how they can be used in the design of a tool that is capable of performing automatic speech communication analysis.

3.1 DATABASE

The database is used at this stage of development to validate noise reduction methods, in particular cross-talk. In this context, the database was also manually annotated in order to compare the algorithm's output regarding speech segments with the real data.

3.1.1 Data

For this study we are going to consider group's communication dynamics in small group meetings. The data set used in this work is composed of audio recorded in small-scale informal meetings. The data refer to a social experiment carried out at the Universidade de Aveiro in which the participants organize themselves in groups of four to perform a collaborative task. Team members are sitting around a table, each of them using a personal headset that is recording their voice. The database totals about 30 hours of meetings in which, for each meeting, there are four times this amount, that is, for each meeting the audio of each participant is recorded, totaling 120 hours of recorded data.

3.1.2 Annotated Data

The development of a speech processing platform consists of several steps where, in each one, there is a set of modules whose operation is based on various audio and speech processing methods. In this regard, several of these methods, e.g., noise reduction techniques, can profit from annotated data to guide development and validate their behaviour. To this effect, manual annotations of a subset of the audio data were performed.

The data annotation process was conducted using the software Praat [51] as depicted in Figure 3.1. Data is annotated in terms of EOUs, that is, for each annotated meeting, each speaker’s start and end of utterance is manually marked. The definition of utterance is kept as simple as possible: an utterance, or turn, is the intentional voiced activity by a participant which expresses its intention to communicate with other speakers. The main point of divergence between different definitions is the identification of the moment when a person ends its utterance. Should it end whenever the person stops speaking for a certain amount of time? Or can he make prolonged pauses and still maintain the “floor”? For reasons of simplification and pragmatism, the annotated data marks an EOU when a person stops speaking for a certain amount of time.

In this work, we considered annotated intervals regarding speakers activity, in terms of utterances, for 20% of the data. This makes up about 1440 minutes (24 hours) of annotated data. These annotations are used to validate the cross-talk and EOU detection methods for this work and can be re-used for future works conducted on the database.

Figure 3.1: Example of 30 seconds annotated audio segment from the data set. On top, recorded signal’s waveform. On the center, spectrogram and pitch formations; on the bottom, annotated intervals. “1” stands for utterance and “0” stands for silence.

3.2 COMPUTATIONAL TOOL FOR SPEECH COMMUNICATION ANALYSIS

The conceptualized approach consists of a framework which provides a programmatic environment, in Python, to process speech in human-to-human communication. It contains a set of methods that have the ability to robustly handle dialogue in real scenarios, using

Figure 3.2: Overall diagram of the proposed framework. From left to right, in a first phase the system reads and processes the audio files in order to extract activity moments from the speakers. It then processes this output to decrease the amount of inter-microphone noise and segments the contiguous frames in turns. Finally, it computes a set of speech features and exports them for analysis. Green blocks represent the components that were developed for this work.

techniques that have proven to be adequate in such cases. They are built using the libraries SciPy and NumPy, which provide the core functionalities for them to work, such as signal processing methods. The proposed solution is intended to be modular and scalable in order to allow future contributions that may improve the techniques used. This approach also allows future works to expand the platform with more functionalities suited for different case studies. Bearing this in mind, Figure 3.2 shows an overview of the proposed solution. The platform is composed of a set of modules that are interconnected with each other starting from the speech signals of each speaker, and is broadly divided in four stages: 1. voiced activity detection; 2. EOU detection; 3. feature extraction; 4. data set creation.

3.2.1 Voice Activity Detection

Voice activity detection, or VAD, is the process of detecting human voice, or the lack of it, in a segment of an acoustic signal as shown in Figure 3.3. This task provides the baseline for many speech processing applications [60] and, therefore, it is of utmost importance that the choice of the algorithm used is as adequate as possible for the application in question. It has been widely studied that different VAD techniques are valid and provide good results but they are also dependant of factors that vary from application to application, such as the amount of noise of the recorded data. There are mainly two broad categories of VAD

algorithms: supervised and unsupervised. The first relates to algorithms that are trained with labelled data of specific data set(s). These type of algorithms will provide good results as long as the “new”, unseen, data is similar to the data that was previously used to train the classifier. Otherwise, its performance may degrade considerably and it may not be better than a “simpler” algorithm [20]. On the other hand, unsupervised algorithms try to generalize the *voiced/unvoiced* decision to match any conditions that it may encounter. Nonetheless, the quest to build a VAD method that is able to perfectly generalize in unseen circumstances is still an ongoing task that is far from being finished, despite the considerable progress that has been made in this research field [20].

The selected VAD algorithm for this thesis is proposed by Tan, Sarkar, and Dehak [20] that proved to yield state-of-the-art results both for noisy and clean speech in generic, real world scenarios. This solution, while achieving very positive results, also takes into account the efficiency with which the classification is made in terms of computing time. This is an important aspect in speech recognition applications, especially in cases where audio files have a considerable duration. VAD algorithms are usually computationally expensive because they perform a series of complex mathematical operations on the signal to extract features on the frequency domain, such as pitch and energy and, thus, it is mandatory to work with efficient algorithms for voice detection.

The algorithm is divided in three stages, as explained by Tan, Sarkar, and Dehak [20]: 1. First pass denoising; 2. Second pass denoising; 3. Voice Activity detection. The first and second stages aim to remove as much noise as possible from the raw signal by making use of noise-estimation, such as SNR weighted energy difference and high-energy segments detection, and speech enhancement techniques. The algorithm’s decision is then based on the pitch and SNR weighted energy difference of the denoised segments obtained from the first stages. Following the good results of the algorithm in generic applications on real-world scenarios, the default settings were used. Nonetheless, as previously mentioned, in scenarios such as the one studied in this thesis, where participants are relatively close to each other, microphone bleeding is a phenomenon that must be addressed in order to guarantee that the resulting speech signal is as close to the real speaker’s behavior as possible, hence resulting in a voice activity detection that more accurately depicts speaker activity.

Figure 3.3: VAD example for a four seconds audio segment. In blue, the audio signal’s waveform is represented. In orange, the VAD output is represented signaling whether there is speech or not.

Cross-talk detection

As a starting point, the VAD output is used by itself to understand how it deals with cross-talk without any post-processing. Soon it was realized that it was struggling by inspecting some conversational features such as speech time and overlapping time between participants, as seen in Figure 3.4. It is noticeable by the figure that the VAD output mistakenly detects speech segments in cross-talk situations. In fact, considering the VAD output, in this segment the overlap between the four participants would be almost total during the whole segment while, from the annotation, it is clear that the overlap occurs only in two short moments. Furthermore, as mentioned earlier, based on previous works it is expected that the overlap might be frequent but short, as in the annotated segment. On the other hand, without any further processing, the VAD output alone generates an overlap ratio of 30% between participants which accounts for an overlap of 20 seconds per each minute of detected speech.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.4: Speech signal comparison between annotated segment and VAD output. (a) VAD algorithm’s output for 4 different speakers in a 10 seconds segment. (b) Annotated data for the same segment. It is possible to visualize that the VAD output detects that the speakers overlap almost in the entire segment while, in reality, they don’t. This figure shows the cross-talk influence on VAD output.

For cross-talk detection, a processing pipeline has been developed that utilizes both the acoustic signal and the VAD output to decide whether a segment is considered as voiced due to cross-talk or not. The pipeline consists of three stages, as illustrated in Figure 3.5, that are discussed below. Furthermore, the process of cross-talk detection is illustrated in the flow chart depicted in Figure 3.6

Figure 3.5: Cross-talk detection pipeline. Diagram representing the three stages of the cross-talk detection’s pipeline.

Then, to detect cross-talk, the first step is to calculate the voiced segments of each speaker that inevitably correspond to moments of single speech, i.e., when only one speaker is active at the time.

From the VAD output, there is the possibility to extract segments that are most likely “clean”, that is, without possibility of cross-talk. The rationale behind this is that VAD algorithms can identify activity even though they cannot distinguish its source. If we discard the segments in which activity is detected for more than one speaker at the same time, we get the parts of the audio in which only one speaker is active. Therefore we have isolated the segments where one and only one speaker is active. These are also referred as “local channel” or “speaker alone” in previous studies [18] while they are referred as **reference** in this work. This information is useful to have because we can use these segments to characterise the speech signals of each speaker which will later help us to detect cross-talk situations. In other words, we can inspect these segments in terms of energy, pitch or any other acoustic feature and compare each possible cross-talk situation for a speaker with its “clean” frames. The second step is to detect possible cross-talk situations for each participant. The detection of possible cross-talk situations is a task that can be done in many ways. The approach adopted in this work is to identify segments in which the VAD has detected activity for more than one speaker, i.e. situations in which there is an overlap between the speech signals of two or more speakers. The question that needs to be answered is: are these overlaps “real” or are they cross-talk? For this, we compare the overlapping segments of a speaker with its “reference segments”.

For each speaker that its signal is overlapping with others in a certain segment, we compare the speaker’s overlapped frames with its own reference segments. The comparison is based on a set of the signal’s features. Namely, we use the pitch and the short-time signal kurtosis to decide if the segment is cross-talk or not. It has been shown by De Leon [61] that the kurtosis of overlapping speech is generally less than the kurtosis of “clean” segments. This was also validated by Wrigley, Brown, Wan, *et al.* [18] who found that the kurtosis was one of the best features to detect cross-talk. Therefore, we can compare the overlapping speech segments with the speaker’s reference segments, which in our work are the “clean” speech utterances. If the overlapping segment’s kurtosis is lower than the reference values, then it is possible that it is cross-talk. We make an additional check by using the pitch of the segment. If the segment’s pitch is zero, then we assume that the overlapping speech happens due to cross-talk. When a segment does not contain any voiced activity from the local speaker, it is more likely that pitch formations are not consistent or even non existing.

Figure 3.6: Flow-chart representing the decision's process of classifying a segment as cross-talk or real overlap.

Measures of cross-talk detection accuracy

One important resource to test and refine cross-talk detection methods is to have an understanding of how much of it is being detected, at each stage, and how it relates with actual cross-talk situations by analysing the annotated audio data. This will enable testing different

techniques in search of the optimal method to use. It should be noted that different methods may be more appropriate for different use cases and, naturally, it is important to study the data in order to adapt the proposed methods to it. As mentioned, for this work we are going to study group meetings where participants are sitting around a table. Each one of them has a personal headset that is recording its audio to a separate channel and, therefore, our audio data has one channel per participant. This has implications in terms of processing because we know, at each time, which microphone is detecting activity and we do not need to use processing techniques such as speaker diarization on the **whole** length of the signals. Moreover, the data set contains annotated data about speaker's activity (as described above), in terms of utterances, that are used to validate the cross-talk and EOU detection methods for this application.

The first step is to define metrics to evaluate the cross-talk detection algorithm and its results: True Positive Rate (TPR), or recall, and False Positive Rate (FPR). The recall, or sensitivity, is an interesting metric to validate the cross-talk detection algorithm's results because it answers the question "from the real *voiced* segments, which ones are correctly classified". It is important to guarantee that the real speech segments that are captured by the VAD are not discarded by the post-processing methods.

On the other hand, the FPR will answer the question "from the frames classified as *voiced*, how many were actually *unvoiced* segments". This is, perhaps, the most relevant measure to take in to account since we expect that there will be some cross-talk, and many segments classified as *voiced* by the VAD will be in fact *unvoiced*.

It is important to keep the FPR as low as possible without decreasing the TPR, as it is an important trade-off that has to be balanced. Moreover, for a more intuitive analysis of these methods, it is useful to use some higher level features to understand the impact of post-processing techniques on aspects that influence the analysis of how the communication is unveiling. In this case, the total speech time and the overlap time between the speakers are considered.

In terms of TPR and FPR, without any cross-talk detection, the VAD algorithm has a sub-optimal performance which is verified by its high FPR of 0.40. It is to be noted that the TPR is also high (0.94) since this algorithm constantly classifies frames as *voiced* due to cross-talk. If an algorithm blindly classifies every frame as *voiced*, the TPR would likely be 1 since every real *voiced* frame is correctly classified. On the other hand, the FPR would be high as well, as in this case, since every real *unvoiced* frame would be wrongly classified as *voiced*.

Cross-talk removal

The cross-talk phenomenon is addressed by using the kurtosis and pitch of overlapping segments, as explained earlier. In fact, comparing with the annotated data, this method achieved a 0.29 FPR while keeping the TPR in 0.81. Compared with the "naive" VAD output, this means that the FPR decreased by 11 percentual points, from 0.40 to 0.29, but, on the other hand, the TPR decreased as well by 13 percentual points, from 0.94 to 0.81. Nonetheless,

this trade-off is favorable since the main problem is the miss classification of *voiced* segments that introduce a considerable amount of error into the analysis of the communication. This means that some information regarding voiced data is lost but, on the other hand, it is able to capture many segments that were miss-classified as *voiced* and, in fact, most of the real *voiced* data is still going to be used. Moreover, the overlapping time between participants went from 20 seconds to 17 seconds per minute of speech.

The cross-talk detection also impacts the total perceived speech by the system as seen in Figure 3.7. Note that with cross-talk detection all the speech time values from the distribution are lower because a lot of speech was detected as being cross-talk and not “real” speech. Note also that the distribution is tighter than in the “no cross-talk detection” scenario, which means that groups speech time are not so sparse, making their speech production behavior more consistent.

Figure 3.7: Speech time difference with and without cross-talk detection. Box-plot representing the total speech time of every group in the present study. On the left, speech time distribution among all groups when cross-talk detection is performed. On the right, speech time distribution among all groups when cross-talk detection is not performed. Values in each box-plot from top to bottom: maximum value for speech time; 75% confidence interval; 50% (or median); 25% confidence interval; minimum value. The green triangle represents the average total speech value among all groups.

The annotated data contains information about the start and end of utterances and, therefore, when the cross-talk detection results are compared with the annotated data, there is another aspect that must be considered: the EOU detection.

There are two notes to bear in mind when analysing these results: i) even for the manually annotated data, there are small errors in terms of frames, since human precision is not exact. At a sampling frequency of 44 kHz or 22 kHz it means that, in the annotation, a frame lag implies an error of 0.04 ms or 0.02 ms, respectively. And ii) the metrics are not weighted, this is, the algorithm’s failures are evaluated in the same manner. In example, a miss-match of one

frame near speech segments accounts the same to the performance indicators as classifying an isolated *unvoiced* frame as *voiced*. This increases the chance that there are small mismatches between the speech detection of the algorithm with the annotated data and, as the metrics are not weighted, these small errors can have a considerable negative influence on the results.

3.2.2 End of Utterance detection

To build a tool capable of analyzing communication in groups, it is necessary to design a framework that represents speech and dialogue to enable the extraction of conversational features in a methodical and concise way. Firstly, voice activity leads to voiced segments. Then, it is important to identify turns, to enable an analysis focusing on the conversational structure of the dialogue. In this regard, it requires deciding when they start and finish, which can be performed joining contiguous segments of speech.

Communication perceived in terms of turns is an intuitive approximation on how it is performed between humans [25]–[28]. Moreover, “turns” makes it possible to extract a set of conversational features that can model some interactions between participants solely based in their turns. Turn-shifting mechanics can dictate the flow of a conversation and might be, by itself, an indicator of social dynamics between speakers. In example, if one speaker has longer and more frequent turns than the other participants, it can be seen as a possible indicator for dominance or leadership. While speakers that tend to grab the floor, i.e., start talking after long periods of silence, are seen as more proactive and display more initiative than others.

The task of detecting EOU, as discussed earlier, requires certain parameters to be established. That is, the beginning of a turn will always be the moment when a person starts talking but, on the other hand, the end of that turn may not be so simple to detect. People have moments of pauses during their speech, either because they are thinking and formulating what they are going to say, or because they are concentrating on another task and their speech production process is slower, among many others factors. Therefore, it is not possible to define the end as the moment when a person stops speaking because it might be splitting one speech turn into two or more. It is, then, necessary to define how the algorithm will classify a frame as being the end of the utterance.

This task can be performed using simpler approaches where a fixed silence threshold is used. For example, in this work we consider a silence threshold of 0.5 s [36]. If a person is engaged on a speaking turn and then stops speaking for more than 0.5 s, that utterance is considered to be over. On the other hand, if the pause is shorter, the person maintains the speaking floor and it is considered that the person is still on its turn. This behavior is illustrated in Figure 3.8

Figure 3.8: Speech signal segmentation into a single turn. On top, speech signal’s output without EOU detection. On bottom, “turn” signal containing the start and end of utterance for the segment’s speech. Small pauses between speech segments are ignored because the silence time is smaller than the specified threshold of 0.5s.

Moreover, it is also defined the minimum turn length that a person can have. The rationale is that an utterance is a segment of speech on which a person is intentionally communicating with others. If a single frame is detected as *voiced*, it would mean that a person spoke for 0.04 s (for a sampling rate of 44 kHz), which is not realistic. In addition, another source of error would be introduced by small, isolated observations of voiced activity that would be considered as speech turns. In real environments it is possible that there are small disturbances in the microphones that activate the voice detector, in which case we do not want to consider them as speech turns. Take as an example the data set used for this work in which several situations were detected in which participants trigger the VAD without having communicated with the other participants. It was found that the participants in such meetings are usually untrained in the usage of microphones and breath and contact noise are frequently observed [18]. Furthermore, it was also noted that participants in the creative thinking process may sometimes have small interjections and produce brief moments of self-talk, i.e. they have no intention of communicating with the rest of the group but produce voiced activity that is detected and must not be considered as speech, since it would introduce error while analysing speech and turns. Therefore, it is also defined a minimum amount of time that a person must speak in order to be considered a turn, as seen in Figure 3.9. For this work, this threshold is 0.6 s. It is to be noted that small interjections, such as “mm-hm”, are part of the communicative process and have a practical usage, such as agreeing, and, with this threshold, they are discarded. In this work, we have no interest in studying this particular phenomenon and, therefore, as mentioned earlier, these parameters should be adapted to each study in order to fit its needs.

Figure 3.9: Speech signal grouping in to turns, ignoring small *voiced* segments. On top, speech signal’s output without EOU detection. On bottom, “turn” signal containing the start and end of utterance for the segment’s speech. Small *voiced* segments are not considered part of an utterance because their length is smaller than the specified threshold of 0.6 s.

Based on the VAD binary output the next task is to group contiguous segments of speech, where two segments are considered as contiguous if the silence gap between the two of them is less than the established threshold. Note that there are other approaches for this entailing different levels of complexity. As an example, Meshorer and Heeman [35] extract a set of conversational features, such as the relative turn length, and then use its values from the two previous utterances to predict when the current utterance will end. The authors define this by using the past speaker behavior to predict the EOUs. Nonetheless, there are many SDSs that still use fixed silence thresholds as an approximation for this task and this was the method of choice for this work. Nevertheless, the proposed analysis methods adopt a modular approach, since it is important that the system is open for considering new methods, in the future, and the consideration of different EOU detection techniques with minimal integration efforts for the user is possible.

3.2.3 Feature extraction

In this section some features that can be extracted from the audio and turn data described above will be covered. For each feature an example of its usage will be presented, as well as examples of social behaviors that may be represented by each of them.

The creation of a logical structure that represents the communication from the point of view of turns allows the extraction of descriptive characteristics of the speech sustained between the different members of the group. These characteristics aim to quantify various aspects of speech that allow their computational analysis in a following phase and, therefore, the extraction of these characteristics should always be done in a way that tries to represent the communication, as best as possible.

However, the term communication is a wide-ranging term, so it is necessary to consider which aspects of it are to be addressed. That is, the features will depend on the study to be carried out because different aspects of communication are more representative for different study cases. Consider the study conducted by Aldeneh, Jaiswal, Picheny, *et al.* [13] in which patterns of interaction between patients with bi-polar disorder and psychotherapists are studied. The authors study how conversational patterns change over the course of clinical sessions in which patients have pronounced emotional fluctuations. For this, it was useful to use representative characteristics of the dialogue, such as the number of times the patient and his therapist alternate the speech turns. This type of features are referred to as **dialogue** or **conversational** features.

Other features can also be extracted directly from the speech signal. It can be useful to understand how the participants' voice behaves over different turns and in different situations. For example, let us consider an overlap between two people. If the overlap is natural, in agreement, people do not consider the overlap to be an aggressive signal and therefore this will be reflected in how that person reacts to the overlap, which will likely be with a calm reaction, thus keeping its voice under control. On the other hand, if the overlap occurs in a situation of conflict it is plausible that the person has a more aggressive reaction and can raise the tone of their voice. The idea is then to capture some characteristics in situations that may be relevant to the communication analysis. This type of features are referred to as **acoustic** features.

Dialogue features

The first step is to define a set of metrics that will help us to analyse individual's behaviors and their interactions. We are looking for clues to assess people's stance in a meeting, their role within the group, how they interact with the rest of the group, among others. The ultimate goal of these features is to support the detection of individual communicative patterns for each person and how they shift and adapt throughout the duration of the meetings.

These characteristics are mostly derived from the notion of turns and we study their behaviour both from an individual point of view as well as relative to the other members of the meeting. Considering the context of this work, and the relevant literature, the following features were implemented:

- **Speech time.** It represents the total time of produced speech by each person. It is one of the most generic features in the sense that many others can be derived from it. It is reported as an indicator of dominance in groups [39] and it is correlated with the group's cohesion levels [9]. Therefore, although it is one of the simplest characteristics, it is also one of the most useful and at the same time most intuitive to use and, when dealing with communication, it is a good starting point to explore diverse communicative phenomenons.
- **Total overlap time.** It is equivalent to the total time when two or more people overlap when talking. It is seen as a frequent phenomenon in multi-party conversations such as meetings [18] and, similarly to speech time, is one of the characteristics that allows more

derivations from it. Moreover, the overlap alone is a phenomenon that can be studied in isolation because it has, in itself, a considerable amount of information regarding social dynamics.

- **Number of turns, average turn length and turn shifts.** Since the study of communication in this work is based on the turn-taking dynamics of the participants, a set of characteristics derived from the notion of turn are considered such as the number of turns, which reflects the total number of speech turns that each person had during the meeting; the average turn length which quantifies the duration of each participant's turn; the number of turn shifts, that is, how many times participants shift speech turns between each other. These features are widely explored in the literature in speech communication analysis in a wide variety of case studies.
- **FCR.** It represents "the relative amount of time that each participant spends speaking to the total amount of speech in a conversation"[13]. It represents how balanced the distribution of speech time is among the participants of the meeting and can, therefore, be seen as a descriptive characteristic of social phenomena, such as leadership or dominance. This feature not only indicates who is dominating a conversation, it can also indicate who will be the next person to speak [35] and how people can accommodate to the dominant speaker based on its FCR [30].
- **Floor Grabs.** When there is a contiguous period of silence and a participant decides to take the initiative and speak, that person is considered to have made a floor grab. Therefore, to define a floor grab it is necessary to determine a minimum silence time that must exist for a participation to be considered a floor grab. If the silence's duration is smaller than this threshold and a speaker takes the floor, it is not considered as a floor grab since small silences between turns and turn-shifts are a natural part of a conversation's flow. It can be considered as an indicator of initiative. For this work, the considered silence threshold is 1.5s [12].
- **Interruptions.** An interruption is defined as a turn transition between participant A and B in which participant A started his turn before B finished his. In this scenario, A is considered to be the interruptor and B the interruptee. Still, it is necessary to differentiate between interruptions and situations in which there is only a natural turn transition, as seen in Figure 3.10, which are expected to be more frequent than interruptions [47]. For this, a time threshold is defined as the minimum time limit for which the interruptee continued to speak before stopping and giving the floor to the interruptor. In this work, a threshold of 0.2s [15] is used. It should be noted that in this definition there is the possibility that natural turn transitions will be classified as interruptions if the interruptor starts its turn almost at the end of the interruptee's. Still, natural (end-of-turn) overlaps tend to be longer than overlaps in abrupt interruptions. The interruption dynamics are particularly interesting since they are associated with the participant's personality traits [15], [44], [46] and dominant behaviors that may deteriorate the quality of the group's communication and consequently their ability to deal with conflict.

Figure 3.10: Overlap and interrupt detection comparison. The grey areas represent overlapping segments. The left-most overlap is considered a “natural” one since its duration (0.4 s) is above the minimum threshold of 0.2 s. In this situation the interruptee finished its turn. On the other hand, the right-most situation represents an interruption since its duration (0.16 s) is below the minimum threshold. The interruptee was forced to finish its turn by the interruptor.

- **Consecutive turns.** It measures the tendency for a person to keep the floor in his possession. A consecutive turn is defined as one that proceeds from the same person without there being turns of other participants between them. This feature can be considered as an indicator of dominance and initiative.

Acoustic features

Besides the dialogue features, it is also feasible to explore the behavior of the acoustic signals throughout the meetings. Furthermore, it is useful to focus on specific parts that might be of particular interest to the scenario, such as overlaps, and to try to understand whether the participants’ voices have a distinctive behavior, at these times. In terms of overlap, the voice is expected to behave differently in situations where it occurs in a natural turn transition than in situations of conflictuous overlap [62].

- **Energy.** It can be extracted using several methods such as the Welch’s method [63] or computing the sum of the absolute signal values. Studies explore the hypothesis of energy being associated with higher levels of group cohesion in meetings [9].
- **Pitch.** As mentioned earlier, pitch can be extracted using several methods, depending on the data’s noise conditions. The pitch with which a person speaks may contain information about their emotional state [13] and variations in pitch may help to identify conflict situations.

That said, the acoustic features can be extracted on a turn-by-turn basis or can be focused in specific segments.

3.2.4 Feature set creation

After the features are extracted, the objective was to export all data in a systematic, organized manner so that they can be used in subsequent analyses, whether be manual or automatic.

Since speech communication is a phenomenon that occurs over time, it was decided to define a strategy for grouping the data in time windows. This strategy allows capturing variations in participants' conversational patterns throughout the meeting that may aid to evidence the manifestation of social phenomena, such as conflict. Moreover, this approach can help the characterization of different contexts that exist throughout the meeting. That is, meetings have a logical sequence of events in which each one has its own context and, in return, each context will influence the speaker's behaviors on the following moments. For example, at the beginning of a meeting participants are still in an introductory process where the levels of language production are not so high. In the study case analysed in this dissertation this introductory process is quite noticeable as the participants have no prior knowledge of each other. This may indicate that they are not familiar with either the other members of the group or the meeting itself. Nonetheless, it is expected that this social constraint will dissipate over time as the context of the meeting will evolve.

Grouping data in windows is also a trade-off between the full raw data and the amount of data that is extracted to carry out analyses. Additionally, many of the features that are deemed for analysing speech communication are richer when computed over a period of time. This decision was also made considering the case of study presented in this dissertation, in the following chapter.

The framework allows the extracted data to be grouped in time windows of fixed size. It is possible to customize the length of these windows in order to be adjusted to the study in question. In this work the windows have a duration of 30 s. The rationale behind this decision is that with smaller windows it is possible to obtain a finer granularity of data that can be later grouped in larger intervals, if necessary. The opposite would no longer be possible. This way, we are able to enrich the data set with these novel data and enable future analysis by different researchers. However, if a different level of data granularity is required, it can always be easily obtained using the developed methods.

When defining fixed time windows, there will be situations where certain phenomena exist between the transition of two consecutive time windows. For example, if a speech turn starts at 27 s and ends at 33 s, then that turn should only be counted in one of the two time windows: before 30 seconds, or after. It has been decided that whatever the event is, be it a turn; interruption; overlap; etc., in which the situation described above occurs, said event will be considered as belonging to the interval in which it started. In the previous case, the turn would be considered as belonging to window 0-30 seconds since it started at the 27 s mark. This allows aggregating data for multiple windows without artificially enlarging the number of turns, for example.

Studying speech communication in groups during conflict

In this chapter a study is conducted on communication in groups during conflict. Firstly, the database used for this analysis is described. Afterwards, the stages of the study performed are detailed. In this context, an individual study is made on each feature of speech and dialogue that deemed relevant. Finally, an automatic analysis is performed to cluster groups based on their communicative indicators to validate the relevance of the different chosen features.

4.1 STUDY CONTEXTUALIZATION AND DATA

In the previous chapter, and for the sake of simplicity, we provided a short overview of the data set being considered for the purpose of providing just enough context for the chosen methods and an illustration of their outcomes. Overall, the computational methods proposed, even though tuned for the particular case of the data set (e.g., cross-talk detection), are general enough to serve any similar case studies. However, in this chapter, we present a first study that illustrates how the proposed computational features can be harnessed to support a deeper analysis of the data to extract knowledge on what is actually happening with the behaviour of the different groups, over time. Therefore, a more detailed description of the data set and how it was acquired is now required to provide enough context for the presented results.

The database used in this work was developed at the Universidade de Aveiro in a collaboration between the Departamento de Psicologia da Universidade de Aveiro (DEP-UA), the Instituto de Engenharia Eletrónica e Informática de Aveiro (IEETA) and the Faculdade de Economia da Universidade de Coimbra (FEUC). In this context, an experimental study was carried out from group meetings with the aim of observing the emergence of potential **conflicts** and consequent strategies applied to their resolution.

The experimental setup comprises groups of four university students, who are total strangers, that must cooperate to accomplish the building of a simple structure using pieces of Lego™. Each meeting is divided into two parts in which the participants are asked to accomplish a different task in each one. Each group is given a set of instructions to build the structure within a time limit, in each task. At the beginning of both tasks, participants have a few minutes to discuss possible solutions to the proposed problem. This is followed by the construction phase of the solution that was agreed upon by the group members. Between tasks, participants are asked to fill out a survey. Participants answered a total of three questionnaires: one before the first task, one between tasks and, finally, one after the second task.

There are three experimental conditions: Control Condition (CC) and two conflict conditions: Relational Conflict Condition (CCR) and Task Conflict Condition (CCT). Martins [64], based on the works by Jehn [65], states that CCRs are a perception of interpersonal incompatibility related to personal aspects of the participants. On the other hand, CCTs stem from disagreement between participants over the task that is required and how it should be addressed and resolved.

The first task is common to all groups. That is, they all start from the same starting point where no conflict is introduced and the proposed task is presented in the same way to every team. During the break between the two tasks, one of the two types of conflict, or none, is induced in the groups. In the case of CCR, individual feedback is given to each participant falsely stating that the rest of the group have a negative perception about their performance, in the meeting. It should be noted that this feedback is forged by the moderators so that a possible relational conflict is incited. In the case of CCT, the instructions presented are unclear and conflictive (e.g., a) the spaceship needs to be of a color that blends with the sky; and b) the spaceship needs to be of a warm color) in order to foster discussion about the different perceptions of what is asked from the participants. If no conflict is introduced the condition is called CC. This type of group serves as a reference for comparison between meetings where, theoretically, there is no conflict with meetings where, potentially, there is some degree of conflict between its members. Each group will either be labeled as a CCR, CCT or CC group.

In order to measure the levels of conflict in the different groups, a set of psychological characteristics are computed from the surveys answers from each participant in the three different stages. These features measure the levels of well-being and the quality of the communication perceived by the participants.

Moreover, audio-visual data was collected from every meeting. In the case of audio, which is addressed in this work, data is recorded using microphones mounted in personal wireless headset microphones. That is, each participant uses a headset throughout the meeting that records his/her voice. The complete audio file of each meeting is then built into a single file that contains one channel for each participant.

4.2 OVERALL ANALYSIS METHODS

Broadly speaking, one of the objectives of this study is to explore the descriptive characteristics of communication that can quantify social behaviors associated with the emergence of conflicts in meetings using the database previously described. More specifically, to understand how these descriptors relate to the different conflict conditions and lastly, based on these characteristics, compare the different conflict conditions in order to highlight potential different behaviors of the groups for each type of conflict.

The framework presented in this work allowed to extract, in a robust and methodical way, a set of features that can potentially answer these questions. The study is divided in two phases: i) in a first phase, manual exploratory analyses are performed that aim to study the conversational features of each participant and their behaviour throughout the meetings. Afterwards, the same type of analysis is performed for each group and, finally, it is done for each type of conflict. ii) In a second phase, an automatic analysis based on unsupervised algorithms is carried out. With this approach, it is possible to verify whether the results of the automatic analysis are endorsed by the knowledge of the characteristics obtained previously, in the first phase.

Before moving to a computational approach to understand the relationship between the speech communication features and the different conditions of conflict, an individual analysis of each characteristic is performed in order to extract as much knowledge as possible about the groups and how they behave during meetings. In this way, the following studies are carried out: 1. detect possible patterns for each feature and observe its relationship with the different moments of the meeting; and 2. compare the behavior of each feature in different experimental conditions. In order to carry out a more general analysis of the conflict conditions, a bottom-up analysis approach was chosen. In other words, as exemplified in Figure 4.1, the conversational features are first computed for each participant in the experiment. Subsequently, these values are grouped together with the other members of the group and, finally, the results obtained for all the groups from the same conflict condition are aggregated. The strategy of grouping the features, both at group and conflict condition level, is done on a case-by-case basis. There is no single formula that applies to all speech descriptors. For example, a group's speech time is the sum of the total speaking times of its participants. In other cases, different measures such as average, median, etc. can be used. These will be detailed in the respective section, for each feature.

Figure 4.1: Example of the calculation structure used. In this example, only one conflict condition (in green) and two groups (in blue) are illustrated. Each group consists of four participants represented in yellow and their dialogue features are represented by individual purple boxes. The feature’s computations are made in a bottom-up approach.

4.3 FEATURE SELECTION TO STUDY CONFLICT BASED ON SPEECH COMMUNICATION IN GROUPS

In this work, a study is conducted on social dynamics associated with group conflict. That being said, we are interested in speech’s descriptors that characterize human behaviors such as dominance, leadership, cohesion and rapport that can indicate the emergence of conflict within a group. In this first study, we focused on dialogue features given their relevance and easier interpretation and judged to be a good demonstration of how the work carried out can be harnessed for research in group dynamics. With this in mind, the analyses performed take into consideration the following characteristics.

4.3.1 Speech time

When a person thinks that the rest of the participants are not happy with its way of working, its reaction to the conflict can be done in various ways that can be captured by its speech time: a more proactive approach, in which the participant tries to compensate their colleagues, that will increase its activity in terms of speech. Or, on the other hand, the person may opt for a more withdrawn, socially closed strategy, which will, evidently, result in a decrease in the speech time. The latter is illustrated in Figure 4.2. The participant 4 (in green) was

very dominant in the first task but decreased his speech time significantly in the second task, which shows that his conversational patterns have most likely changed due to the relational conflict induced between tasks.

Figure 4.2: Speech time for each participant in a group meeting with conflicts. The figure represents a whole meeting of a conflictive group in the current experiment. The y-axis represents the speech time, in seconds, over time windows of 30 s, of each participant. The meeting is divided in two parts: the Task 1, in gray, and the Task 2, in white. Note that between tasks, it was introduced a relational conflict within the group and it is to emphasize the behavior of the speaker 4, in green.

Speech time also allows to capture patterns that emerge naturally in the context of this experience. At the beginning of each experience, the group is in a discussion phase so that the conversational levels will forcefully increase. During the Lego construction phase, people are expected to speak less as they have to concentrate more on building the structure. At this stage, it is also interesting to note that some communicative patterns change: the behavior of turns and silence periods will inevitably change, something that will be addressed later in this dissertation.

In terms of speech time, these patterns are visible in the Figure 4.3. It is possible to notice some communicative patterns: the tasks start with more activity as the participants start by discussing their ideas. This is followed by a less active period in which participants build the structure. In the final phase of construction, participants demonstrate themselves to be more talkative, as can be seen, on the plot, by the upward slopes in the final phases of each task. Since this is an example of a conflict group, a decrease in the conversational levels from the first task to the second task can also be seen.

After calculating the speaking time of all the participants, a group analysis is carried out. To this end, the total speech time of the group was observed, which is defined as the sum of the partial speech times of its members. Again, from this perspective, it is possible to observe some conversational patterns that highlight the flow of the meeting both in response to the

conflict and in the different phases of the experience.

Figure 4.3: Speech time for a single group during a meeting. Representation of a group's total speaking time throughout the meeting. The y-axis represents the speech time, in seconds, of the group as the sum of the speech time of its members. The meeting is divided in two parts: the Task 1, in gray, and the Task 2, in white. Note that the amount of produced speech increases or decreases depending on the stage of the experience.

Finally, all the groups of each type of conflict are grouped. In terms of speech time, the grouping is done as follows: for each instant of the meeting, three percentiles of the statistical distribution of the speech time of all groups of the same type of conflict are calculated. They are the 10%, 50% or median, and 90% percentile. The rationale is based on the fact that, for different types of conflict, it will be interesting to analyse both median and edge cases. Edge cases will be groups where speech production was much lower or much higher than the normal behaviour of other groups of the same conflict condition.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.4: Speech time comparison between different experimental conditions. Representation of the 10%, 50% and 90% percentile of the speech time for all teams grouped by type of conflict. The plots contain the same information, represented in two different ways. In the top one, the different types of conflict are separated into different subplots. In the bottom, all values are overlapped. The CCR is represented in orange, CCT in purple and CC in blue. The blank segment represents the pause between tasks.

It is worth noting that the production of speech by CCR groups in the second task is usually lower than other conditions, especially in the first 10 minutes of the second task. This behavior is visible both in the median and the 10% percentile, as seen in Figure 4.4b. In contrast, CC groups have a higher median speech production than conflict groups. This is particularly striking at times when participants are working. One possible explanation for

this is that, at other times, participants are forced by the experiment to talk and, therefore, the difference in speech between groups is less remarkable. It appears to be a situation where participants in conflict groups withdraw from dialogue at a time when it is socially plausible to do so.

4.3.2 Floor Control Ratio

During a meeting, depending on the reaction of the participants to the conflict, the distribution of speech among members will be more or less balanced. More dominant members tend to talk constantly, preventing other less participatory people from expressing themselves. Moreover, participants that are not willing to cope with conflicts might retreat from the conversation, abstaining themselves from speaking and, thus, giving the floor to other team members. These behaviors can be characterized by the FCR.

For this feature, the feature is described using the median, the 10% and 90% percentiles for each group and condition.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.5: Floor Control Ratio comparison between different experimental conditions. Representation of the 10%, 50% and 90% percentile of the FCR for all teams grouped by type of conflict. The plots contain the same information, represented in two different ways. In the top one, the different types of conflict are separated into different subplots. In the bottom, all values are overlapped. The CCR is represented in orange, CCT in purple and CC in blue. The blank segment represents the pause between tasks.

As expected, the FCR median value is usually around 0.25. For each participant, the FCR is computed by dividing its speech time by the group's total speech time, at the same instant. For this feature, the most notable aspects can be observed mostly in the 10% and 90% percentiles. It is to note that, for every instant, the limits will be symmetrical. That is, if a member takes over the floor control for a considerable period of time it means that other

members cannot talk so much, assuming that the participants do not talk in overlap for a long time.

It was observed that for the case of CCR groups, the distribution of speech among the participants is more unbalanced than for the CC for most of the first ten minutes. It is visible in both the 10th and 90th percentiles in Figure 4.5. If the reaction to the conflict of one of the members is to retract and stay silent as much as possible, then the distribution of the FCR will quickly change in its extremities. On the other hand, if the conflict caused one of the members to try to compensate his colleagues, he will force his control of the floor further. Inevitably, this behaviour will also affect this feature, as previously discussed.

4.3.3 Overlap

From our experience, as communicators, we perceive that overlap during dialogue has negative impacts on communication and that it can be an indicator of a lack of harmony among speakers. However, as has already been mentioned, not all overlaps have this negative character and, therefore, it is important to understand and define which situations are to be considered. In this case of study, the most interesting overlaps will be those that occur over a considerable period of time because they are a phenomenon which does not respect the social rules of turn-taking dynamics in dialogue. For this, the periods of overlap greater than 1 s between any members of the group were then calculated. The group overlap is calculated as all segments in which there are two or more members speaking simultaneously for extended periods of time. This feature is not computed starting from the individual's values, as in the previous cases. If speaker A and speaker B overlap for 10s, then both have an overlap of 10s. On the other hand, the group overlap is not 20s. In fact, the overlapped segment has a total duration of 10s.

Figure 4.6: Group overlap time comparison for all experimental conditions. Each line represents the average group overlap value for all the groups of a certain condition.

The difference between the conflict conditions in terms of overlap is more remarkable in the second task between 5th and 20th minutes as can be seen in Figure 4.6, especially in the case of CCT groups which have much higher rates of overlap than the other conditions after the initial discussion phase. Since groups from this condition need to discuss the conflicting instructions, they might extend the discussion phase longer than groups from other conditions and, since instructions are not clear, it is expected that members will have different ideas that are likely to collide with each other, creating more overlaps than the other groups.

4.4 AUTOMATED ANALYSIS USING UNSUPERVISED ALGORITHMS

On the basis of the analyses carried out previously, an automatic analysis of the data was then performed using unsupervised learning algorithms.

4.4.1 Unsupervised approach

In this context, the K-Means clustering algorithm was explored. This algorithm allows data sets to be grouped based on their features. For the case study in question, the aim is to cluster all the groups into three distinct clusters, one for each conflict condition. In the ideal situation, if the different experimental conditions have a very different impact on the groups and if all groups for a particular condition reacted equally, one would expect three clusters, each containing all groups for each condition. Moreover, in this scenario, the distance between clusters should be as large as possible so that the conditions of conflict are very different from each other.

The clustering procedure will be tested for a wide range of dialogue feature combinations to understand the different way the groups are clustered. More specifically, it might help to expose the relevance of each set of features, and time intervals, on the analysis of the distinct experimental conditions that might corroborate with the hypothesis raised in the analyses previously made.

Features

To work with this type of algorithms, the previously extracted data was grouped in periods of 5 m. For example, the speech time of a group is given as input to the algorithm as the speech time in the first 5 m, followed by the value for the next 5 m and so on until the end of the meeting. For this analysis 30 groups were considered, including 10 for each experimental condition.

In a previous analysis it was possible to observe that, for some characteristics, there was more variation between the types of conflict for extreme confidence intervals (5% and 95%). For other features, mean, deviation and median analyses showed some promising signs. For all characteristics there were indications that the variation was greater at some time intervals, specifically in the second task.

In a first stage, the following characteristics were explored: 1. speech time; 2. floor control ratio; 3. overlap time. For each of these characteristics, it is necessary to aggregate the values

of each group in five-minute intervals. This is done using statistics of each group's values in each interval, as explained below.

In the case of speech time, the mean, median and confidence intervals are calculated for each interval. For the floor control ratio only the confidence intervals were used because the median seems to offer very little information. Finally, in the case of overlap, the mean was used.

Evaluation Metrics

In order to compare the different results obtained from the unsupervised learning algorithms, it is necessary to establish a set of metrics that allow the quantification of each cluster's behavior and of each set of features used. Hence, the following metrics have been defined:

- Silhouette score - this metric evaluates the cluster's formations. It takes into account the average distance of the groups in each cluster to the center of their respective cluster (intra-cluster distance). On the other hand, it measures the distance between different clusters (inter-cluster distance). Broadly speaking, it evaluates each cluster's density and the separation of different clusters. This metric values range between -1 and 1. Results around zero indicate overlapping clusters and the result is higher for cases where clusters are denser and well separated.
- Homogeneity - This metric indicates how homogeneous clusters are in terms of types of experimental condition. For example, if each cluster contains only groups of one condition, then the homogeneity is 1 (or 100%).
- Completeness - this metric indicates what percentage of groups of the same experimental condition are grouped in the same cluster. For example, if all the groups of each condition are grouped on the same cluster, then the completeness is 1 (or 100%).

In addition to these metrics, it is relevant to evaluate the results from a macro point of view. Since we will perform clustering for different combinations of dialogue features and time intervals, we will evaluate the clustering results by each interval and feature. The idea is to try to understand the relationship of the results with specific features and interval ranges to verify if the patterns detected by the clustering method resemble those that were manually observed during the exploratory analysis.

4.5 CLUSTERING RESULTS

During the course of this study some very interesting results were obtained. These results are characterized by high values of the metrics mentioned in section 4.4.1. The analysis of the results are carried out taking in to account intervals of 5 minutes. The aim is to understand whether for different experimental conditions the differences in behavior are a constant phenomenon or just occur for specific time intervals. Additionally, these results will be interpreted according to the expected behaviors of the different phases of the meeting's course. This approach enables us to understand what is happening on each stage of the meeting and how it relates with the results obtained. More specifically, we are able to assess which

speech indicators better describe the behavior of the groups from the different experimental conditions in each stage.

A great majority of the best results are focused on time intervals in the seconds task. This validates, as expected, that the second task contains richer information on how the different experimental conditions behave. Moreover, it also shows that, in the first task, groups are not supposed to be distinguished between themselves given that the exact same initial conditions were accomplished for every group. Therefore, the following results refer only to the second task of the experiment.

4.5.1 Experiment time 0 to 5 minutes

In this stage, the participants are encouraged to discuss their proposed solution for the task at hand. It is expected that teams will be more active, in terms of speech, that could possibly help in the task of detecting conflicts.

Cluster	CCR	CCT	CC	Median Speech (s)	Median Overlap (s)	FCR Interquartile Range
0	0	6	8	4.43	1.96	0.55
1	7	3	2	3.48	0.84	0.69
2	3	1	0	3.14	0.35	0.74

Table 4.1: Cluster results for the experiment interval 0 to 5 m considering the speech and overlap times. The median speech and overlap time are higher in the cluster 0, which is composed mainly of CC and CCT groups. These values are lower in the cluster 1, which is composed mostly by CCR groups. Cluster results have a homogeneity score of 0.292, completeness of 0.324 and silhouette score of 0.537.

As mentioned above, the first five minutes of the experiment is a time interval in which participants are forced to speak by the very nature of the experience. Despite the fact that the speaking time increases forcibly, it seems, by the results shown in Table 4.1, that the conflict has not manifested itself in CCT groups since they are paired with groups of the CC condition. They are still discussing the instructions received and comparing their approaches to the problem, hence the higher values of median speech time and overlap. On the other hand, the CCR group members already know that other members disliked their work or their attitude and, therefore, it is likely that the conflict is already present within team members at the start of the task. Therefore, their attitude is affected and this is perceived by the lower median speech time that, in turn, explains the lower median overlap time. If teams talk less, they will likely overlap less as well. Nonetheless, there are four groups (three CCR and one CCT) that are separated in a distinct cluster. This may be due to the fact that relational conflicts are more personal and the attitude that a participant has towards it is more unpredictable, as mentioned earlier. As a result, their median speech and overlap time are even lower than the groups in the cluster 1.

4.5.2 Experiment time 5 to 10 minutes

Groups start the building process, distribute tasks and start gathering pieces for the construction. It is a transition phase where members start by talking more and decrease their speech

activity over time, as the work progresses. It is expected that the communicative patterns will be different between teams that are having conflicts and teams that do not. Moreover, conflicts are expected to begin to manifest themselves - if they did not already - especially in groups that had not previously shown signs of conflict, as the CCT groups.

Cluster	CCR	CCT	CC	Median Speech (s)	Median Overlap (s)	FCR Interquartile Range
0	0	6	3	2.16	4.00	0.47
1	10	1	2	0.86	2.70	0.61
2	0	3	5	1.23	3.41	0.53

Table 4.2: Cluster results for the experiment interval 5 to 10 m considering the FCR and overlap time. The median overlap is considerably lower within the cluster 1, which contains all the CCR groups, while its FCR inter-quartile range is higher. The median overlap is higher in the cluster 0, which contains mostly groups from the CCT. Cluster results have a homogeneity score of 0.394, completeness of 0.403 and silhouette score of 0.379

It can be seen in Table 4.2 that in the beginning of the building process, the clustering results in three clusters that contain mostly groups of the same experimental condition. This indicates that during this phase, the experimental conditions are more easily distinguishable between them. The CCR groups are all clustered together, 60% of the CCT groups are in a single cluster and 50% of CC groups are together as well.

It seems that each condition starts working under different circumstances. In example, CCT (cluster 0) groups may still be discussing the instructions, speaking and overlapping more as seen in Table 4.2, while the CCR groups, clustered in cluster 1, have a more unbalanced distribution of speech time, explained by its higher FCR interquartile range, which can be interpreted as a manifestation of the teams relational issues. Moreover, this cluster also has the lowest median overlap which may be related to the fact that CCR groups are less active in this phase, as seen by its lower median speech time, hence overlapping less.

4.5.3 Experiment time 10 to 15 minutes

This is the peak moment of the building process. Each member, theoretically, already knows his task and is focused on building his part of the structure. It is expected that members will discuss less in this phase since they will be more focused on the task at hand. However, communication is still relevant and it is expected that teams with less harmony levels will be distinguished from non-conflictive groups.

Cluster	CCR	CCT	CC	Median Speech (s)	Median Overlap (s)	FCR Interquartile Range
0	2	0	0	3.14	5.28	0.51
1	7	5	7	0.65	3.24	0.57
2	1	5	3	1.85	3.65	0.49

Table 4.3: Cluster results for the experiment interval 10 to 15 m considering the overlap time. There are two main clusters: cluster 1, containing groups from the three experimental conditions, and cluster 2 containing mainly CCT groups. There is one cluster, cluster 0, that contains only two CCR groups. The median overlap and speech times are considerably lower for the cluster 1. Cluster results have a homogeneity score of 0.117, completeness of 0.155 and silhouette score of 0.580

As seen in Table 4.3, there is one cluster, cluster 1, that contains more than 50% of the groups of every experimental condition. This cluster is characterized by a lower median speech time and considerably lower median overlap time, which may indicate that these groups are less active in this phase. For CC groups, this might happen simply because they are working and do not have a lot to talk about. On the other hand, conflict groups might talk less due to the conflicts that they have. These results validate the hypothesis raised above which states that groups are less talkative in this stage of the meeting. However, there is one cluster, cluster 2, that contains mostly CCT groups. In contrast to the cluster 1, this cluster is characterized by groups that have higher speech activity, visible by the speech and overlap time, specially CCT groups. This is possibly a consequence of groups from this condition tending to discuss the instructions for longer periods of time.

4.5.4 Experiment time 15 to 20 minutes

At this moment, groups are notified by the moderators that they have 5 minutes remaining to finish the building process. The group behaviors are expected to be more fuzzy since they will depend on how the work is going. There are two cases that deem plausible: i) groups that are working over the clock either start talking more, if they are still trying to finish the structure, or talk less if they already gave up; ii) groups whose work is going smoothly are expected to talk more since they are almost finishing.

Moreover, conflict groups that are under-performing, i.e. whose work is not evolving positively, might show behaviors that flag the existence of conflicts.

Cluster	CCR	CCT	CC	Median Speech (s)	Median Overlap (s)	FCR Interquartile Range
0	5	3	3	1.27	4.29	0.54
1	5	3	4	0.48	2.82	0.63
2	0	4	3	0.99	3.62	0.47

Table 4.4: Cluster results for the experiment interval 15 to 20 m considering the speech time and FCR. There are distinct clusters containing groups from the diverse experimental conditions. Cluster results have a homogeneity score of 0.106, completeness of 0.109 and silhouette score of 0.372.

In terms of speech, groups are more active compared to the previous interval, as seen in Table 4.4. On the other hand, the overlap and FCR values differ between clusters, hence corroborating with the idea that groups are more unpredictable at this stage. Additionally, the distribution of groups by the three clusters is also more heterogeneous, that is, no single cluster is able to aggregate more than 50% of the groups from an experimental condition. This behaviour is perceptible through the analysis of the clustering evaluation metrics, more specifically the homogeneity and completeness, that exhibit the lowest values of all the cases analysed. The cluster formations are also not very evident among themselves, which is reflected in the low silhouette score they present.

4.5.5 Experiment time 20 to 25 minutes

These are the closing moments, where groups already stopped working and are discussing small details about the experience before proceeding to answer the surveys. Groups that did not achieve their goals might show signs of discontent, hence highlighting their conflict experimental condition.

Cluster	CCR	CCT	CC	Median Speech (s)	Median Overlap (s)	FCR Interquartile Range
0	3	4	8	2.00	4.62	0.42
1	0	0	1	0.02	0.50	0.97
2	7	6	1	0.94	2.99	0.54

Table 4.5: Cluster results for the experiment interval 20 to 25 m considering the FCR. There are two main clusters, cluster 2, composed mostly of CCR and CCT groups that has the highest FCR inter-quartile range, while the other is composed of CC groups. There is another cluster, cluster 1, that contains only one group. Cluster results have a homogeneity score of 0.159, completeness of 0.214 and silhouette score of 0.356.

Using the FCR in the last 5 minutes, it is possible to separate the conflict groups from the control groups properly, as seen in Table 4.5 in the cluster 2. Nonetheless, it should be noted that conflicts are not distinguished and end up being clustered together. This highlights that CCT groups behave as CCR by the end of the task something that has developed perhaps due to differences in viewpoints and perspectives in relation to the task, which was given with confusing instructions. It can even be interpreted that this type of conflict can generate relational conflicts that are most evident at the end of the task when the outcome of the experience may not have been the most satisfactory for the group. These conflict behaviors are described by the highest FCR interquartile range value, which means that the distribution of speech time is more unbalanced. This cluster also presents considerably lower speech and overlap times.

4.6 FINAL REMARKS

In a first analysis, it has already been possible to obtain results that provided new insights on the data, as well as validate some hypothesis that were raised in the exploratory analysis.

Firstly, it is confirmed that the second part of the task is the one which allows us to better differentiate between groups of distinct conditions. This study also allowed us to explore a little the notion that groups from different experimental conditions are more easily distinguished at certain times of the experiences. That is, just because a group belongs to a condition does not mean that the group behaves differently throughout the full duration of the experience. The group can oscillate between moments more similar to control and moments more characteristic of the condition to which it belongs.

In this line of thought, the best results show interesting and promising perspectives. The behaviour of the CCT groups starts to be similar to the CC groups while in the beginning of the meeting, when groups are still discussing their approaches. Throughout the course of the meeting, approaching the final stages, their behavior shifts and they act in a similar way to the CCR groups which indicates that conflicts may have manifested themselves during the meeting. This indicates that conflicts related with the task may be transformed into relational conflicts between team members. This behavior is depicted in Table 4.6.

Interval	Clusters	Description	Indicators
0 to 5 m		CCT groups are clustered with CC groups.	CCT and CC exhibit higher speech and overlap times.
5 to 10 m		The different experimental conditions are separated into three clusters.	CCR exhibit lower speech times and higher FCR.
10 to 15 m		Groups show a similar behavior except some CCT groups.	Isolated CCT exhibit higher speech and overlap times.
15 to 20 m		Groups are shuffled, behaviors are more unpredictable.	Clusters formations exhibit the lowest metrics.
20 to 25 m		CCT groups are clustered with CCR groups.	CCR and CCT exhibit higher FCR and lower speech times.

Table 4.6: Overall clustering results. Blue rectangles represent clusters containing a majority of CC groups; purple represents CCT groups and orange represents CCR groups. The columns “H”, “C” and “S” refer to the evaluation metrics homogeneity, completeness and silhouette score, respectively.

In terms of features, there are several interpretations for the results. The first is that different features help to highlight different types of conflict. Therefore, the clustering process needs carefully chosen set of features that help us to better explain the conflict phenomenon. To finish this section, it is worth mentioning that there are several feature vectors that can be derived from the features already considered. For instance, if we consider the speech time we can derive new features such as: difference in speaking time between the first and second

task; difference between consecutive intervals; statistics such as mean, deviation, confidence intervals, etc. These choices might have a great impact on the performance of the clustering process and should be made with criteria.

It is expected that clustering will become more evident and more robust while more data is provided and richer features are considered. Therefore, new features can be introduced that can serve as conflict indicators, such as interruptions between group members and the energy of each speaker during speech overlaps.

Discussion & Future Work

This chapter discusses some conclusions drawn during the course of this dissertation. Followed by a discussion on the contributions made, more specifically the annotations that were carried out, as well as the noise reduction techniques tested and developed, and, finally, the exploration of speech features that found on literature. Lastly, to finish this chapter, some topics are addressed related to future works that can be performed on top of the one described in this dissertation.

5.1 DISCUSSION

The proposed objectives of the study for this dissertation were contemplated and achieved in a satisfactory manner.

On the one hand, the exploration of communication in group meetings proved to be a great challenge from the point of view of both technical implementation and theoretical formulation. From a theoretical point of view, communication is a complex and complicated process subject to different interpretations and analysis. However, the techniques used, mostly based on the literature, allowed the conceptualization of communication in order to explore the social dynamics that were intended to be studied in the case study. From a technical point of view, very challenging obstacles also arose. First of all, audio recordings in real life scenarios are likely to contain a large amount of unpredictable and unexpected noise. Nevertheless, the results obtained in the reduction of inter-microphone contamination were in line with what was expected from studies found in the literature [18].

Throughout the work described in this dissertation, there was always a concern, from the engineering point of view, to keep the solution as abstract and open as possible in order to allow adaptations and future contributions. Moreover, the manipulation of audio implies a considerable volume of data that constantly challenged the platform. In this context, it has always been mandatory to implement efficient solutions that keep in mind the limitations imposed by the audios.

From the point of view of the descriptive characteristics of the communication, both its definitions and implementations proved to be satisfactory for the study in question although not all of them were studied in the final phase. The manual analysis made it possible to formulate some hypotheses that were later validated by an automated analysis with unsupervised algorithms. The way the conflict manifests itself is indeed spontaneous, as expected. That is, there are periods when groups from the distinct experimental conditions behave in unique ways while, in other time intervals, they resemble other conditions. On the other hand, it was not always possible to separate all the groups perfectly. There are two hypotheses that can be explored: i) on the one hand, the conflict induced by the experiment may not have had an effect on some groups and, therefore, their behaviour will not be similar to other groups in which the conflict had an impact. ii) the results obtained may in fact be a mirror of reality. The groups are conglomerates of people and each person has very distinct personality traits. This means that different groups in the same experimental condition may have very distinct reactions to each other.

5.2 CONTRIBUTIONS

Annotated data. A set of annotations to the database used in the case study was also performed. These annotations enabled the validation of some methods used in this dissertation, namely the cross-talk reduction and turn segmentation algorithms. This contribution may be useful for future works that might profit from having annotated data to perform new studies.

Data pre-processing. This dissertation was an exploratory work in which various aspects of group communication were addressed in working meeting scenarios. To this end, a framework has been developed that is able to process meeting audios in a reliable and robust manner. It is prepared to deal with some noise, more specifically cross-talk, that is inherent to recorded audio in real environments, while keeping a reasonable amount of the processed information. The cross-talk detection techniques employed in this work were based on literature, which allowed to test methods that deemed relevant and validate their performance in cross-talk detection.

Dialogue and acoustic feature selection. Based on literature regarding social dynamics in group meetings, it was possible to identify several speech features and test a set of methods for their extraction. Additionally, a study was carried out on groups to better understand the social phenomenon of conflicts that, in turn, was based on studying the groups behaviors described by these features.

5.3 FUTURE WORK

In fact, one of the perceptions that became evident during the course of this dissertation was the fact that the study of communication is as complex as the authors want. Communication is a very rich phenomenon, with many plausible study components. From the physical and biological process of speech production to the study of conversational patterns, there are many

topics that can always be studied and that can add value and knowledge to our understanding of communication.

First, for cross-talk reduction there are a number of speech features that can be explored such as entropy [24], cross-correlation metrics between channels [18], among others. Moreover, the techniques used to explore these features can be more complex. In particular, it is possible to use statistical models that allow modelling the different cross-talk scenarios and that transform the problem into a classic classification task.

In turn segmentation, once again, there are many other approaches to what was presented in this dissertation. The approach proposed here is more classical and is based on static techniques, that is, fixed time parameters are defined for the detection of EOUs. However, in the literature, very interesting technical proposals have been made that setup the algorithm in a dynamic way using the local and global features of each participant's speech [35].

The definition and usage of the descriptive characteristics of the dialogue are also plausible for discussion. On one hand, the features can be re-defined and parameterized in different ways to what was proposed in this dissertation. However, the most interesting aspect here is the introduction of new features that can add value to the study of communication and social dynamics. In example, even though the acoustic features were not used in the conflict detection study presented in chapter 4 they might provide useful insights in future works that can extend this one. Moreover, both the features proposed here and future contributions can always be seen from different perspectives. It is possible to calculate the same features at different times in order to focus on some phenomena such as overlaps or interruptions.

The framework proposed in this work can be reconfigured and used with other databases in order to exploit other phenomena. And, in this context, the study of social dynamics can be carried out using other techniques and taking advantage of other features that are more appropriate to the problem in question.

Finally, throughout the experiment, the participants answered a set of questionnaires including a self-assessment of the amount of perceived conflict. This data can be harnessed to enrich the study conducted in this work and improve the interpretability of the results obtained. More specifically, its information can be exploited, alongside the automatic analysis, to understand whether the conflict conditions have been properly induced in the groups, hence explaining the clusters behaviors.

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